

MYTHÓS AS AN ELEMENT OF EPISTEMIC AND EMPIRICAL FORMATION

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511690

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Philosopher. Political Scientist. Researcher. Email: srgrdriguesdesouza@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of *Mythòs*, as an element that is capable of building the intellectual and empirical transformation of individuals, when inserted in a society, where there is the issue of collectivity as a point of existential balance. Its scientific relevance is presented in terms of promoting a new discussion about the tales of Antiquity and how they guaranteed the existence of people even when the law did not yet exist as a determinant of life and customs and, even after these emerged, how they continued to be useful for maintaining political governance in the City-States. Its social relevance lies in clarifying to the broad public that the Myth is not a fantasy and meaningless story. It contains a truth, understood in classical semantic terms as memory and that it stores the events and facts of the past and how they influenced the lives of all members of the community. This is a bibliographical, factual research, based on systematic studies and a hermeneutics directed to the topic in question. It is very innocent to associate the birth of Greek mythology with the practice of writing, because in no people, known and studied anthropologically, are myths linked to such a selective act as this. The myth was, in Greek culture, linked to the sociological aspect of society, as a whole, and not linked to the individual psychological aspect of the character, for the simple fact that there was no this type of feeling of particular belonging. Every citizen was an essential part of the Polis, that is, their life was directly linked to it and everything that happened.

Keywords: Mythòs; Greek mythology; Memory; It was from myth.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this text is to present a philosophical, systematic study, which addresses myth and its variations as an investigative theme, seeking as the main source for understanding this object the understanding of pre-Homeric myth and its correlation with human education, understanding the term as the integral formation of the human being, over time. The preparation of the human being, from choosing the place where he decides to live to where he decides to be buried, is full of symbolic elements, all very important to him, and this entire subjective condition of relevance becomes the object of explanations, the most varied, which They are

dressed in all kinds of costumes and charms. This entire epic apparatus was called *Mythós*, which is not just any tale; It is a story that aims to be true and, therefore, it is understood that it becomes perennial, that it is not forgotten.

The objective we wish to achieve, with this article, is to bring, to the light of Logic, the need to once again treat myth as a foundation of the organization and human intellect-cognitive formation based on the educational experience of children. Different from being seen and treated as a fantasy story, devoid of empirical meaning, the myth is the compilation of real events that affected the lives of great heroes or even entire civilizations, and the way of storing such situations in the collective memory has been transformed. In stories marked by intense magic.

As human cognitive potential advances, the search for answers accumulates; however, their ability to answer such questions is impeded because of the instruments they do not have available and that is where myths come into play, not as a consolation for their ignorance, as some geniuses in the wonderful lamp like to burp; but, as an instrument that can provide him with satisfaction and pleasure and can still be manipulated, improved according to the increase of his intellect and that, given the splendor of its construction, became easier to remember, because the way in which had enchanted the first person who heard it, it could enchant others and thus, the transmission of knowledge followed an always continuous line.

The human psyche has very simple characteristics, what causes it to be treated with such deference is the fact that it is not possible to decipher it, which leads to bizarre interpretations, giving it an air of high complexity. In the early days, there wasn't much that attracted humans' attention, other than their main objective, which was to survive in a supremely hostile world. For example, the buildings they lived in were not beautiful or distinguished, which did not arouse his curiosity about how they were built and, in addition to all this, he had to constantly fight to have what was necessary for his survival in terms of nutrition, always watchful, lest he himself become the meal of some ferocious animal.

As his intellectual and cognitive capacity, combined with his imaginative production, began to produce ideas in his thinking, beyond the things that his myopic eyes contemplated; however, he was unable to distinguish in his distinct immaturity. Human hormones, especially adrenaline, when in dangerous situations, tend to play countless tricks and produce visions that go beyond reality. Reports from survivors of risky situations are always exaggerated in their efforts and the dangers they were subjected to far beyond their ability to overcome, requiring actions that completely defied all human logic and the limits of their potential.

In order to enlighten his companions about the world that was opening up before their eyes, he created a tale: which was exactly the genesis of explanatory myths and with this, seeing that they became convinced of what he expressed and told, he took it as a point of departure. Ignition for the creation of others and transformed them, much later, into an instrument of domination and control over their peers.

This exhibition addresses the fact that the myth was, possibly, the first artifact and educational act that human thought, still childish in its construction, created, in order to understand the infinite mysterious universe that opened up in front of it. . So that myth is a historical construction as primitive [*understood here, in this term as ancient*] and, paradoxically, as young as the complex human Reason itself of elaborating thoughts [*the development of the cerebral cortex*] and applying them to the improvement of its means of life [*development of intellect through and from practical action*].

Even before speaking, the fact of prolonged fixed observation of the stars already led those beings with very simple explanatory needs to create conjunctures about what everything that surrounded and enchanted them would be and why it attracted their attention. It was his ignorance; above all, the origin of the universe worried him and ended up forcing him to develop a form of explanation that, despite all the scientific and technological evolution, still enchants with the same overwhelming power that it exercised over the *sapiens ancestors* .

It is necessary to clarify that the principle of human evolution is based on phylogenetic and ontogenetic bases. So one can therefore assume the emergence of myth as a way of appeasing the curiosity of human beings; however, it was not born as an express tale, but rather as an individual mental tale ; since the speech was not yet articulated. From its development, they began to express it as an exercise in coexistence, then as action and forms of political articulation.

It is very innocent to associate the birth of Greek mythology with the practice of writing, because in no people, known and studied anthropologically, are myths linked to such a selective act as this. Myths begin to be reproduced in records, books and canons due to their intellectual and political strength, being used as instruments for indoctrinating faith and transforming social mentality, an object of mass domination.

It is with John Locke (1632-1704 dH), David Hume (1711-1776 dH) and Friedrich Nietzsche (1844-1900 dH) , the philosophers who most understood the development processes of the human *psyche* throughout history, that the relevance of myth is officially presented, as an elementary part of the construction of personality, intellectuality and the capacity for cognition. It allows us to explore what lies beyond, at the same time as it provides relief for the

spirit in search of truth, understood in classical Greek terms : *post-mortem* memory , remembrance through songs, greetings made through hymns and through poetry, narrated and sung by aedos and rhapsodes.

THE MYTH

Myth, as a phenomenon, is a subject that proves to be of extreme academic relevance, since the overwhelming majority of educational educators (teachers at all levels of education) in the fields of early childhood education, in particular, do not know the etymological and semantics of the word *myth* ; therefore, wanting them to know its definition and its importance in the construction of a *psyche* that is in a clear process of formation is demanding beyond the limits promoted by the academic and cultural technical training that they have.

Added to this is the fact that with the advent of Christianity and its variants, myths that were found outside the Old and New Testaments were considered lies, fantasies and created a concept of Truth that contradicted the content of these books, which is false, that is, a dogmatic teaching model was created where what is said or told through Christianity is true and what is said and told through myths is a lie, pure and simple.

possible space for more in-depth discussions about cultural products expressed through myths was destroyed . From an early age, children are already bombarded with the fixed and immutable idea that myth is equal to lie, a meaningless fantasy invented by someone who wanted to teach all kinds of dogmatism .

However, very different from this, myth is a way of narrating any fact, more specifically, it focuses on the phenomenon, in an attempt to explain it, as long as it occurred at a given moment and in a given space that, for some reason, an alien motive, ignored by everyone, influenced the life of the community; therefore, myth is an explanatory element of the origins and reasons for things and phenomenological events, that is, it attempts, in a sensible and equitable way, to achieve an explanation for the natural and supranatural events of everyday life.

Thus, if considered solely as a phenomenological element, the myth is subject to scientific, philosophical and conceptual interpretation, but what hides in the shadows of the mythological construction is its logic, which can only be explained through of belief in the fantastic, that is, when one literally dispenses with rational understanding and adds to the whole the belief in the object told and in the magic expressed by the poet. With this, the myth in its original form and proposal is not to be read by anyone, except by an initiate , an artist, or a

snake charmer who, through his technique, is able to persuade his listeners of the veracity of the facts he narrated.

The first expression, *in strictu* of the Greek myths that dealt with a story of an empire and its fall (the city of Ilion), which included a body of gods and men gladiating among themselves, was the work *Iliad*, in which Homer narrates the saga of the hero Achilles and other demigods, in an insane battle that lasted 10 (ten) years. The Trojan War begins because of the anger and desire for revenge of two goddesses who were denied their beauty in such a contest, by Paris.

There are several versions for the destruction of the city, which took place behind the scenes of Olympus, where some versions narrate that Zeus allowed his protected Polis to be destroyed by Hera and Athéná in exchange for him being able to destroy a city that was protected by his sister and wife whenever he so desired. Others narrate that Hera deceived the Father of the Gods with her orgiastic arrangements and then drank him with ambrosia and made him fall deeply asleep, so that he could not protect Ilion: when he woke up his city was in ruins.

Both tales are part of the classical Greek tradition; but, the one that comes closest to the Homeric tradition is the first one exposed in the previous paragraph, where trickery and deception were qualities extremely appreciated by the Greeks. Later, when they begin to develop politics, the poets adapt the stories to the interests of the strategists. This only reinforces the thesis that changes in the structure of myths were being made adapting much more to political and social moments than to historical [*temporal*] moments in isolation.

I would like to clarify the dilemma created here, that speaking of the political moment and the historical moment as being dichotomous can lead to a serious error; However, what I draw attention to is that political effervescence can change over many years [*advancing or delaying*] strategic processes of changes in thought and adaptations to the times, something that, when left to follow its natural course, would occur; however, not so early, finding everyone, or the majority, completely unprepared to, at least, understand the processes that now appear as recurring phenomena and that require attention from political agents.

In Greece, it was from Homeric texts that myths began to be treated as objects of deeper analysis and poets began to have the opportunity to complement their explanatory spaces [*which could be called empty*]. JJ. Rousseau, in his work *Essay on the Origin of Languages*, raises the question of whether Homer knew how to write; This is an easy question to answer, because writing arrived in Greece and, in particular, in the city of Athens, which was the cradle of Greek civilization, shortly before the time of Socrates, which is proven in the resistance that this philosopher, still, he suggested adhering to the new method of recording his thoughts and

even among the Greeks, adherence to the new system was generally feared for fear of reprisal from the gods.

Taking into account that the *Iliad* was written around the year 1215 (before Hypatia) ², it has clearly been demonstrated how great the resistance was by the Athenians in relation to records through spelling. For a long time, the *Iliad* and the *Odyssey* were the two academic books of Greece and this situation leads me to assume and deduce that they were not, only, because of their depth and peculiar literary characteristics, but because they were the only ones in All country.

Myths assume an extremely important place in Greek written literature during the tragedies, a period in which Athenian theater flourishes and becomes exuberant. The artists needed *scripts* , *scripts to follow*, *to represent the lines and as the tragic poet was given very broad [almost unrestricted] freedom* , to alter the original tale at will and in accordance with the demands of the staged play, the polis began to demand that the original texts be compiled, so that the originality of the myth, which represented its history of traditional culture, was not lost. A classic example is the tale about *Oedipus Tyrannus* , in which in the same year that Sophocles won the prize, seven versions of the myth were represented .

Almost perfect in their gnosiological construction, the spaces left in the lectures referred to how the gods emerged, how they were born and the misadventures between them, such as, for *example*, the clashes between Ares and Athená and even the genealogy of the gods. Poets had to engage in an incessant search for creations and lucubrations, which were capable of satisfying the ever-growing curiosity about the origin of facts and in order to justify an *almost infinite war* .

To end this war, he had to look for mythical elements capable of motivating soldiers on one side, *which possessed such artifacts, considered to have supernatural powers* , and intimidate opponents. Not to mention that they had to appease the pride of the Trojans with a legend about their non-belief, when Cassandra, a soothsayer or prophetess , warned the kings of Troy about their invasion by the Greeks and their consequent and inevitable destruction. But, here is a paradox, because Destiny being an inexorable force, even if they believed in its prophecies, there was no way to change what was outlined by the Moiras, because no one, neither men nor gods, ever escaped their Destiny after being born and/or been created.

²“ I am dating my texts from the cruel murder of Hypatia, of Alexandria (355-415), as being the moment when there was a drastic change in history” (Dr. Sandro Dau, 2023, in personal communication to the author). Under the guidance of this illustrious Researcher and Mentor, from this work onwards, the aforementioned historical dating was adopted as a stylistic standard.

With the suppression of the ordeal and the creation of Destiny, as an inexorable force, which not even Father Zeus could escape its determinations, the myths had to be adapted to such a format that they took on the status of classical literature, in which the poet he would have to use all his stylistic expertise to adjust events to the predicted oracles.

This leads to the deduction that the creation of Destiny was the element that provided the literary search for myths, but making adjustments to their conformation in such a way that they adjusted to the thinking that was being formed in the Polis. It was necessary to create an organization so powerful in its imaginary aspect that it could explain and even justify the excessive actions of the heroes, leading them to punishment for their excesses, since their existence [along with *all their fates, successes, glories and sanctions*] were already pre-determined by an inexorable force, even though the gods and humans used the most diverse means to try to escape this condition.

With this, the myth of the hero begins to need a preamble, a back story, which is intertwined, intellectually and artistically, in such a way that it dispels any and all doubts about the terrible fate that befell a man who appears to be just. . However, this individual's past is a mystery to everyone and, therefore, it was necessary to create some situation in which either he or some direct ascendant had succumbed to evil, so that some evil predicted about him, in the form of revenge, would occur. to reach it, because this had become part of his destiny.

The myth was, in Greek culture, linked to the sociological aspect of society, as a whole, and not linked to the individual psychological aspect of the character, for the simple fact that there was no this type of feeling of particular belonging. Every citizen was an essential part of the Polis, that is, their life was directly linked to it and everything that happened. Even their apparently more selfish attitudes were products of behavior governed by tradition and, if nowadays there is always a mistaken interpretation of the actions of historical characters present in the tales, this is due to this lack of knowledge of the sociological conditions of Antiquity and, for Worse still, they try to analyze and interpret them using a science that did not exist at that time, which leads to mistaken understandings about the people of the past and their customs.

The role of myth is to keep the tradition of people alive, through perfectly elaborated stories, even if it can be said that they are inventions of a warning nature. When the hero is punished for his excesses and arrogance against the gods [or for some other reason of serious offense to the social order], as is the case of Laius, in which his relationship with the son of King Chrysippus, leads the boy to suicide, in turn harming the entire city, because the succession to the throne had been put at risk. Oedipus's father receives a curse through no fault

of his own in the death of his host's son; but because it caused a serious political situation that could result in risks for the entire city and its citizens.

The myth was linked to something much higher than the individual, it explained how the cosmic order had been shaken by an unreasonable act and such action had put the entire system at risk, and for this reason this citizen should be punished, in an exemplary manner, in order to that his attitude did not encourage others to follow him and his ideas and attitudes. The punishment could even be disproportionate in relation to the crime committed; but, the issue was focused on the political imbalance unleashed on the Polis and all citizens, who would start to live in greater fear of their manes and protective gods, because the cult would be tainted and this could arouse their anger.

This leads to a *sui generis interpretation* of how the myth was read and how it should be read and understood by citizens. When they arrived at the theater, the very careful Athenian State soon became the main patron, in order to control the message that would be transmitted through the scenic representation. As a result, many of the versions that have survived to this day are versions adapted for the tragic plays presented at the festival of Dionysus and in the panaternálias. These were already directed with a particular bias, already very different from that which was in the original story.

HOW MYTHS WERE READ

The episodes of the great heroes, which were narrated by the rhapsodes and aedos, were sung, following a musical meter, so that the objective of the action was achieved, which was to awaken the pathetic in the listeners. In the *Odyssey*, when Odysseus hears the stories of the great hero of Ithaca, who had been lost at sea after the end of the Trojan War, narrated, he bursts into tears and the singers think they are acting in a negative way regarding the expression of poetry, he expresses his apologies and when the musicians return to narrating their deeds, he cannot stand it and another interruption occurs, which leads us to deduce that the narratives were intended to awaken joy and happiness, as a consequence of deep feelings of Pride for your heroes.

The way myth was seen by the people of Antiquity and the respect devoted to it, as an element of truth, leads us to understand that they were not read; were interpreted and, if the idea seems confusing to the reader of the 21st Century, constructed within a Cartesian and positivist scheme of education, in which the interpretation of a text comes from its reading, for the Greek, possession of the story related in the tale was he had anticipated a powerful *pathos*, a deep

feeling so intense that he felt ecstasy when he came into contact with the story. He was transported in time and space to where the adventures and battles that involved the spirit of the warrior-god, the character of what was narrated to him, had taken place.

The reader/listener of the tale was taken by this feeling, which made him become involved in the legend and, perhaps this is the cathartic state produced that Aristotle (799-737 aH) says was observed in spectators as an effect of the representation of tragic plays. in the theater of Dionysus, in which these were adaptations of myths, involving great public heroes of Greece. All of this could be the result of public education, in which care was taken to impose respect for tales from an early age, as a legitimate duty and this care began to be treated as a tradition among people, even reaching the days of Classical Antiquity, in Athens and in Greek territory and remained for a long period, despite the aggressiveness with which it was fought by the sophists, who, apparently, their target was not the story; but, this feeling of burning passion with which he was treated and admired by the people. There was no way to destroy faith in the myth; All that was needed was to put an end to the enthusiasm present in reading them for the interest in them and their interpretation to collapse. This is what has reached the present day, when a classic tale from Antiquity is read like any other literature, devoid of emotion and intoxicating feelings. Hence saying that they are just imagined and meaningless stories is nothing more than a common expression and popular rhetoric; part of the discourse that was created many centuries ago and that survives not because it is true; but, due to the fact that the adversary she faces also survived and still maintains the power of seduction and charm, over the human unconscious, as powerfully as it was in its golden days .

Ancient people believed in *Mythós* , because the truth was recorded there and, as mentioned above, the meaning of it was memory, that is, the characters portrayed in the tale were alive and still protected their land from all evil. Therefore, why did the heroes presented end up being punished so severely at the end of the stories? It is here that it is necessary to clarify that, as soon as politics took on a new format in the Polis of Athens, giving rise to democracy, there was a need for some strategy that could control the people's feelings towards submission and, in the same wake , which would not allow them to rebel against the Tyrant, since the Archon-King had already fallen into disgrace along with his instruments of terror.

Myths were chosen as these instruments dedicated to this purpose, because until that moment they were not taken as canonical objects; they could express a certain degree of sacredness, a type of unknown *pathological power* that was manipulated over the population by priests; but, they could be changed according to the convenience of a ruler, in favor of their private and/or political interests.

From all the above, it is clear that the myths were narrated with maximum sentimental expression by the poet, because the ultimate purpose of such an act was to provoke commotion, to awaken the pathetic, the deepest and most unknown feeling that each person carried with them, leading spectators to ecstasy, delirium, tears, confusing their existence with those presented as lived by the characters in the stories.

Much was lost when they removed this *pathological aura from Mythòs*, a work well carried out by Greek philosophers, baptized by Plato as sophists and who, later on, the Catholic Church and institutionalized Christianity took care to define as a standard for their reading and interpretation. They have come to mean nothing, not even as an object of scientific study they have value, because once incapable of arousing emotions, they are not capable of provoking curiosities, conflicts in analyses, in their interpretations and in the way they are understood; since an inferiorizing value judgment had already been imputed to them and ratified by modern science itself, a slave that lives on conventions and conventionalisms.

THE AGE OF MYTH

Myths represented truth for the Greeks of the Archaic and Classical Era. Truth here, understood in its cultural semantic principle that meant *memory*, that is, through them the great heroes of the past, so important for the maintenance of freedom and power, were remembered and honored. For this reason, even with the advent of *logos*, the myth resisted all attacks against it, remaining eternal in its truth.

It is very interesting to clarify what this much-vaunted advent of *logos represents*, in which the expectation was created that everything could be answered with maximum clarity and understanding, a fact contrary to what was stated in relation to *Mythòs*, in which the answers arising through the tales needed to be deciphered and yet they remained taken by an enigmatic tone, subordinated to the humor, always very volatile and fickle, of the gods.

Logòs only seemed like an innovation at the time, and it still continues to be interpreted that way, due to the lack of any element that could oppose it. After its appearance, every time *Mythòs* was invoked as an explanation mechanism for any phenomenon, it no longer had enough power to determine the conviction, because it was possible to demonstrate, through experience, how things happened and even be determined, Preview; in other words, the gods began to lose their element of surprise over human spirits.

All the passion imposed in the mythical story, during the rhetoric of the aedo and the rhapsode, gave way to the coldness of the philosopher, who explained the phenomena and their

intercurrences or recurrences, in which the hand of men and gods had no determinism about them. . This meant that citizens were no longer frightened by the stories and, over time, began to see them as fantastic tales, a way of amusing their children and even admonishing them, since they continued to believe and get excited when listening to them.

It's a complex, and meaningless situation to believe that the intellectual replacement of *Mythòs* by *Logòs* was something thought of as a way to destroy the first. When one carefully analyzes the entire path of cognitive and intellectual development of human beings and, especially of great cultures, one can see that this change was something that was demarcated by the quests that men of science of these times sought and that , inevitably, they would end up catching up. So much so that they did not lose sight of their attraction to poetry, music, and theater, which is born, disappears and is reborn centuries later, bringing the themes and plays represented in Antiquity, which were reenactments of the myths that they so despised (*sic*).)].

As strange as it may seem, it was during the moment of the emergence of philosophical thought, as a way of explaining the universe and its coherences and inconsistencies, that *Mythòs* exerted its deepest charm; because the State and the Tyrant, fearful of losing their power, took care that they were presented to everyone, in a different way, *a priori* ; but, with the advancement of democracy, it became open to all citizens, possibly which meant that they remained alive in the people's memory, no longer as stories, but as plays; however, the message transmitted, despite being somewhat directed towards the strategos' political ideals, still supported a set of ideas about deities and their mechanisms of interference in human existence and life.

This clarifies that *Mythòs* never surrendered, in fact, to an ideological precept that was focused on individualism, remaining, in its synthesis, focused on the ideal condition of the city and the preservation of culture, showing how much the Greeks were linked to pragmatism. Perhaps, for this reason, *sui generis* , he was kept alive in Athenian society, which changed its behavior and ways of facing reality beyond all other city-states in the region. It wasn't a simple matter of respect; it was what was special about it and that, absent all other forms of thought, there was nothing known that could replace it.

EMERGENCE OF THE MYTH

When there was a need for a more complex political organization of people, myths became fantasy stories created from everyday life that were exclusively available to family

members, as a form of entertainment, a way of bringing people closer together. , as well as a moral compass that served as a guide for the difficult decisions that had to be made .

With the advent of population growth and the organization of small clans becoming phratries ³and then cities ⁴, reaching the point of becoming cities, the tales took a more sophisticated direction and a different ideological purpose; This purpose became to maintain control over everyone without the need to use explicit violence.

It was in Athens that this strategy became more noticeable, because there was no concept of private there, everything was public , and everyone who lived there was a citizen; therefore, the polis did not have the power and authority to use unjust force against citizens. Thus, the way of maintaining the established order had to be under the focus of some existential action , which acted on their ways of thinking , in a subliminal way, capable of motivating them to respect their peers and the rights of a citizen .

The *Mythòs* brought this tone very explicitly, highlighting in their conclusions that whoever disobeyed the gods and/or the laws of the city and, even if, in some way, he interfered in this, there would be a severe punishment against the arrogant and not there would be nowhere to flee, because the hands of destiny would reach him, enforcing, to the letter, the sentence handed down against him.

From this element that was present in the structure of mythical thought, the Greeks were able to coordinate their cities and their people for centuries and, it is when the *Logòs* appears , that all its splendor begins to crumble, since the enlightenment was given by the investigation and interpretation belonged, freely, to whoever wished to take possession of it and as they saw fit. The people were given a type of power that they had never even dreamed of and, once they had managed to express their ideas and questions, a historic revolution was underway that could never be stopped or have its ideological direction changed.

Mythòs itself , once a sacred element that was heard and the story related was a warning, becomes the object of studies by philosophers regarding its content and, in the hands of Aristotle of Stagira and his disciples, many of the miracles and incomprehensible situations, treated Sometimes as a curse, sometimes as a gift from the gods, it starts to be interpreted as a product of psychiatric pathologies, in which the collective character of the tale loses its strength, giving way to individualism, an open field for the birth of psychology. The concept of society, based on the *We* begins to disappear, a new one emerging in its place, based on the *Self* .

³Phratry is the meeting of several clans.

⁴Urban is a geographic and social environment characterized by a strong population concentration that creates an organic network for the exchange of services (administrative, commercial, professional, educational and cultural).

It was not *Mythòs* who had changed, it was the society that sheltered him that had suffered interference in his way of behaving and, with this, many things, previously prohibited and, guarded by some kind of *taboo*, were losing their mystical strength, because the feeling of man, in relation to mysticism had been weakened to the point where he doubted its strength and thus placed it under question.

When the Greek *Mythós* were resumed in Rome, they were already in the form of stories with a pedagogical bias and, for there to be a condition for canonization of such stories, it was not very difficult, as it was no longer possible to alter the stories, as they did the aedos, the rhapsodes and the tragic authors, from Classical Antiquity. For example, there is the myth of Adonis, which is an adaptation of the myth of Persephone and Demeter.

The *Mythòs* were created respecting the precepts of human existence and, as laws and social customs were produced, the reports contained in them had to be adapted to fit the norms of the people to which they referred. Even when prejudice is present, the hero enforces the sentence against the arrogant, because that is what the law determined and the report had to be faithful, culminating in the appropriate adjustment to what was prescribed as an order. Everything that is explained by a myth is directed towards a certain end: to warn and ensure that humans remain under the domain of the protective god and not deny them the due offerings, not allowing them to fall into oblivion, because such a situation would mean death for them.

That said, it can be inferred that this was another condition for the myth to become so important in ancient classical culture; It represented a way of keeping the traditions, culture and principles of the people alive.

The myth, in Athens, unfolds in various formats, always being told according to the political changes that occurred at each time. That didn't mean it lost its magic, because each strategos who assumed power needed to be protected by faith and magic.

BIRTH OF RELIGION IN GREECE

From the moment that some families become powerful in Attica, when the cults carried out by them begin to be imposed on subordinates beyond their domestic borders, this particular culture is disseminated to other citizens, foreigners and even in other spheres. . It was in this way that the Greek religion was born and solidified in its first moments, and then the Athenian religion that culminated in the Hellenic culture, that is, dominated and dominating through those families that inhabited the Acropolis (the sacred mountain) took meaning. .

The gods began to be treated in their epics as anthropomorphic beings who carried out adventures with humans, mocking them, humiliating them, sacrificing them and, equally, giving them endless blessings. In the same proportion, the gods helped the heroes to overcome obstacles that would be impossible to overcome without their express help, as when he advises Ulysses to put wax in the ears of his sailors to resist the song of the Siren Parthenope and the warrior himself gods. to eat an herb that would protect him from the magic of the song.

When you look closely at these stories, you realize that they are no longer part of the *Mythòs* , but rather extensions of them, in which the adventures of a god-man are narrated, facing terrible dangers, while being protected by the domestic god, the one to which your family worships and prays for. When *Oedipus the King* was adapted for the theater, its grandeur is due to the fact that, despite already representing the narrative of a complex story, its entire original scope remains very faithful to the roots of the ancient *Mythòs*, those with which most citizens were accustomed to hearing it since their childhood.

It is clear in this tale that there is no interference from the gods, in order to [*try*] to change the course of the fateful destiny that awaited the hero of the plot, much less to console the tyrant's spirit when the truth is revealed to him. To the same extent, Oedipus does not try to break the law; his honor is recognized by all; in such a way that he is granted the right to leave the city in peace, guided by the hands of his daughter Antigone.

The emergence of the religious spirit in Greece, in addition to that which gave honors and asked for protection from the manes, that is, when it is transformed into politics, destroys the primitive *Mythòs* , having to follow the Homeric tradition of writing and representation, in which the gods they become protagonists in the political confrontations that follow in the councils. As Greek society, especially Athenian society, was transformed, the tales were adapted in such a way that a broader knowledge of domestic political life was required in order to be able to understand the elements they contained.

How can we even understand all this change as a recurrence of the advancement of political thought, which was being influenced by thinkers from other parts of Greece and who found in the city of Athens a joyful stage to present their ideas. This whole situation produced a more complex, deeper story with more intertwined elements, which reveals an intercurrent in the way of thinking and living the existential condition.

The most interesting thing is that all of this happens at a time when the transition from oral recording to graphic recording of events, tales and tragic pieces is taking place, in which the State creates a department so that all of this can be properly archived . It may be that such elements introduced into the *Mythòs* were done on purpose, knowing that, after that moment,

there was no longer any way to infer changes, since consulting the originals was no longer restricted to the ability to remember the facts or even subject to thought manipulation.

What must be clarified, for didactic purposes, is that the original *Mythòs* did not contain political disputes in its reports, making the relationship between man-nature and man-society intensely present. Most of the tales that have come down to the present day and that have been taken over by literature in order to be interpreted are stories created with the intention of showing the political strength of some Greek aristocratic families over others.

In this sense, the reports of the infinite fights and intrigues between the gods were, in their internalization, feuds and power disputes between the Athenian aristocratic families who were protected by the respective divine beings who fought, or even fights and domination of entire peoples. However, here we are already distancing ourselves from the pre-Homeric myth, where there were no (so) particular interests and at the same time with intentions of maintaining the social order, such as blind obedience to the system that commands the *polis* .

The narration of myths, before the publication of the Homeric books, had the main objective of fun and appreciation of art in different ways, because they are permeated in the instruments played by the musicians and in the orality that was the responsibility of the poet. Therefore, even if someone wanted to make a deeper reflection on the story and the facts narrated, such an act would be camouflaged by musicality. Furthermore, the question of *logos* does not yet exist, especially in relation to myths, which are considered sacred elements that carry within them a truth, a mnemosyn about a historical past relevant to the *polis* .

Again, it is necessary to clarify that *Logòs*, by itself, was not responsible for *Mythòs* ' removal from public life. The diverse and intense political and thought changes that affected Greece, starting in the 11th century (AH), allowed them to be adapted to new times, now with a shade of fantastic literature; however, devoid of their aura of absolute power. This did not make the original tales disappear; they only remained present in oral form and, with the decline of Greece and its consequent domination by other peoples, much of that wonderful culture was preserved and another part was integrated into the customs and legends of other peoples, leaving, for the future, several expressions from the same story.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MYTH

In the conception of some theorists, myth is characterized, especially, by this ability to allow it to be modeled-remodeled, changed, added to and reduced by subsequent generations , which makes it adaptable to the most varied moments in human history and especially to the

political and social transmutations of each era. This fact occurs because there is an entire framework of events that, through the poet's expertise, is intertwined until forming a perfect consonance of ideas and arguments. With this, it becomes evident that once read in a simple and linear way, like entertainment literature, the myth is not at all or very little capable of awakening the pathetic in the individual, not achieving its objective, which is to indoctrinate and disciplinary, contributing to the maintenance of social order.

Nowadays, myth is seen as an object of study, something very valuable and that allows the very deep interpretation of human customs, behaviors and thoughts of and about a time, allowing us to get closer to very precise readings of what was happening. in the intersubjective spaces of human existence. At that specific moment, its function was to not allow the death of tradition, the death of the warrior and the death of the generations that preceded the men of the present, in which the word death was determined under the semantic concept of *oblivion* (Lettes). In this, these wonderful stories, the heroic and formative tales of *Physis* had the power to keep alive in the memory of all members of the community their primitive genesis, in which some god had saved them or some ancestor and this allowed them to overcome the risk of end of existence.

The main characteristic of myths is that they are created as an oral narrative, in which all linguistic and bodily elements are worked on, with the aim of provoking and awakening terror, compassion and a sense of belonging in the listener. Behind the story was the mime, the orality, the tonality, the poetic depth and it was this that made the entire entanglement narrated enchant those who were present.

The myth presents, represents and re-presents a broadly complex stylistic, epistemological, gnosiological, aesthetic and phenomenological structure, because it is a synthesis⁵, a mixture of reality covered by a fantasy aspect and, at the same time, a fantasy that is being used as a means of transmitting a profound truth.

The forms of myth that have reached the present day are, in their overwhelming majority, the remnants of Greek tragedy, the Hesiodic tradition, poetic literature under the organization of Ovid who brought together part of mythology and ornamented it with literary poetics and fragments. of pure religious mythology, dressed with a golden veil in order to cover up what it kept as specific, which is the sovereignty of the gods, but that much deeper than all this was the supreme and obstinate maintenance of priestly power, that is, what arrived Until us

⁵“Synthesis, derives from the Greek word *synthesis*, which refers to conclusions that are not final in themselves, and never result in absolute truths” (FAZENDA, Ivani Catarina Arantes. *Interdisciplinaridade : story, theory and research*. 11. Ed. Campinas: Papyrus, 2003, p. 40).

it is a very complex tangle that it is barely possible to distinguish between the original tale and the extent to which it was manipulated in order to satisfy the needs and desires for dominance of a certain political group .

The myths were collected from various cultures, in which the situation experienced by certain warriors from distant peoples was similar to that experienced by heroes of stories in other cities; They could even be adaptations of traveling poets, interested in exalting a member of the community they arrived in, in an attempt to draw attention to themselves and their talents. Thanks to these storytellers to the sound of the lyre, many facts were revealed and disseminated throughout the territory until those who were part of them became a legend, in the same way that many natural symbolic elements were brought into everyday life. as a way of representing occurrences linked to existence.

CHANGING THE MYTHS

When playwrights and tragic poets bring together myths in order to perform them, many parts are adapted and others suppressed according to public acclaim and/or refutation. The Hellenic religion also takes over the mythological framework and uses it as a way of masking the maneuvers carried out by the priests against traditional laws. For example, incest was strictly prohibited, but it occurred on a large scale, as it was a way of maintaining the royal lineage and as a way of avoiding a scandal and legal punishment, a mythical tale involving a god was used, where he created From this, the myth of the hero's birth and all the persecution and aversion to the social fact were transferred to some jealous god who undertook all kinds of actions in order to destroy that hybrid, that emulation of the gods. The poet used his poetic license to create something wonderful, transferring social pathos to some wrathful and angry god.

This type of myth became *a conditio sinequa non* for holding priestly positions in the Ancient Age and this custom survived until the 20th century in the most traditional societies . The future national sovereign could not be the son of mere mortals; at most, one of its parents should be of divine lineage. Otherwise, there would be denial of his command by the population. The fact is that humans fear divine wrath so much, due to the volatile mood of the gods, that they expect their political leader to be someone to whom they listen and acquiesce, because there is a blood bond between them. Finally, Aristotle (799-737 aH) was right when he stated that, “man created the gods and gave them his feelings” (2007, p. 38).

This is already a late perception, when religion in Greece was in decline, precisely because the sophists, prior to this philosopher, had called into question much of what was

believed in relation to them. Furthermore, Aristotle was not read in the city of Athens, which this intellectual obscurantism allowed him to write with his pen, considering that the censorship policy imposed by Plato no longer burned works by his ideological rivals and, perhaps, for this simple In detail, his works have survived in Arab countries, reaching the present day through the Romans and the Catholic Church.

CONCLUSION

What we sought to address in this article is how *Mythòs* became an element, from very ancient times, to be an important element in the construction of societies, both in terms of knowledge and in terms of experiencing their customs and practices. social, whether and their religious, natural rites and connection with ancestors and with their own individual history.

An entire intellectual construction had to be elaborated, so that the story served a specific purpose, which in its beginnings was very simple and objective and, as societies transform, assuming a greater degree of complexity, these also they need to be adapted, in order to meet the new understandings and demands of the City-State, which had become the center of the world, taking the place of *Physis*, although still dependent on it.

It is from the poet Homer (1343-1313 aH) that changes are introduced in the *Mythòs* , transforming them into classic literature, supplied with individualistic and very complex feelings for the man of that historical moment, since he was completely unaware of the issue decision-making process about your life and the events related to it. The tale starts to be interpreted by philosophers and has a deeper truth hidden between its lines.

REFERENCES

ARISTOTLE. *The politics*. São Paulo: Escala, 2007.

ROUSSEAU, JJ. *Essay on the origin of languages*. São Paulo: Editora Nova Cultural, 1999. (*Os Pensadores Collection*) .